

A NEW CONVOLUTIVE BLIND SIGNAL SEPARATION ALGORITHM BASED ON SECOND ORDER STATISTICS USING A SIMPLIFIED MIXING MODEL

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a new convolutive blind signal separation algorithm is proposed, which is based on a simplified mixing model and second order statistics. The simplified mixing model uses the fact that the acoustic transfer functions from a source to two closely spaced microphones are very similar. Only one difference between these two functions is needed. The algorithm is efficiently realized in frequency domain and its effectiveness is shown by the experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

A growing number of researchers have been attracted to the problem of blind signal separation in recent years because of its numerous possible applications. Blind Signal Separation (BSS) deals with the problem of separating independent sources only from their mixtures while both the mixing process and original sources are unknown. For acoustical applications, BSS can be used to extract the individual speech signals from multiple microphone signals when several speakers are talking simultaneously. Both the acoustic transfer functions and the source signals are unknown and the available microphone signals contain a mixture of sources. A BSS system of this function under real world conditions could be used, for instance, in a transparent communication system [1].

For stationary sources, Higher (than second) Order Statistics (HOS) are required to achieve the separation. Many existing algorithms are quite complex because of using HOS information explicitly [2] or implicitly [3][4]. However, as shown in [5] and later, for example in [6], Second Order Statistics (SOS) is enough if the sources are nonstationary. The use of only SOS reduces the computational complexity and an implementation of separation algorithms in real time becomes possible. In this paper, taking feasibility into account, a new adaptive BSS algorithm is presented, which is based on a simplified mixing model using only SOS information.

The simplified mixing model (SMM) uses the fact that the acoustic transfer functions from a single source to two closely spaced microphones (say a distance of sev-

eral 10cms) are very similar. Only one difference between these two transfer functions is needed. We realize our algorithm efficiently in frequency domain and estimate all parameters using a gradient descent algorithm. To avoid being trapped in local optima during delay adaptation, we also combine a genetic algorithm with the gradient descent algorithm. The effectiveness of this algorithm is shown by experimental results.

2 NOTATION

Time and frequency signals are denoted by lower and upper case characters respectively. A character representing a vector is underlined. A matrix of filters in time domain is represented by a boldface upper case character, while its frequency domain version is denoted by a curlycue upper case character. $(\cdot)^*$, $(\cdot)^T$, $(\cdot)^H$ and $(\cdot)^{-1}$ denote complex conjugate, matrix transpose, complex matrix conjugate and matrix inverse respectively. The symbols $*$ and $\cdot$ represent convolution and matrix multiplication.

3 SIMPLIFIED MIXING MODEL

Usually a mixing process can be modeled as follows:

$$\underline{x}(t) = \mathbf{M} * \underline{s}(t), \quad (1)$$

where $\underline{s}(t)$ is an n -dimensional vector of mutually independent source signals and $\underline{x}(t)$ is an n -dimensional vector of sensor signals. $\mathbf{M}$ is an $n \times n$ matrix, each element of which is an unknown transfer function. In our case, $\underline{s}(t)$ and $\underline{x}(t)$ represent human speeches and microphone signals respectively. The transfer functions in $\mathbf{M}$ are unknown room impulse responses. Here the same number of speakers and microphones are assumed.

In [7], the relationship between the two room impulse responses obtained from one single source to two microphones has been studied, which was based on room acoustics analysis. The conclusions drawn there are briefly explained as follows.

Given two room impulse responses $h(t, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}')$ and $h(t, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}'')$, where t represents time and $\mathbf{X}$, $\mathbf{X}'$ and $\mathbf{X}''$ denote the locations of the speaker and two microphones, respectively, then

Conclusion 1. in an anechoic environment, $h(t, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}'') = k \cdot h(t - \tau, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}')$, where $k > 0$ is a constant factor and τ is a time delay;

Conclusion 2. in a reverberant environment, if $\mathbf{X}'$ and $\mathbf{X}''$ are different, $h(t, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}'') = \Delta h(t) * h(t - \tau, \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}')$, where $\Delta h(t)$ is an IIR filter. Furthermore, if the distance between $\mathbf{X}'$ and $\mathbf{X}''$ is small enough and/or the reflection coefficients of the room are small enough (for example, in a weakly reverberant cavity), $\Delta h(t)$ can be approximated with an FIR filter.

Applying the above conclusions, (1) can be rewritten as the following,

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{x}(t) &= \underline{x}_s(t) + \underline{\phi}(t), \\ \underline{x}_s(t) &= \mathbf{D} * \mathbf{H} * \underline{s}(t). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$\mathbf{D}$ is an $n \times n$ matrix of filters $D_{ij} = \Delta h_{ij} * \delta(\tau_{ij})$, where τ_{ij} is an unknown time delay which is assumed to be integer multiples of a sampling period and belongs to $[-\tau_{max}, \tau_{max}]$. $\delta(\cdot)$ denotes a delta impulse signal and Δh_{ij} is an FIR filter as described above. For the diagonal elements of $\mathbf{D}$, $\Delta h_{ii} = 1$ and $\tau_{ii} = 0$.

$\mathbf{H}$ is an $n \times n$ diagonal matrix from which the diagonal elements h_{ii} 's are unknown room impulse responses from speaker i to microphone i .

Equation (3) is the so-called SMM from which $\underline{x}_s(t)$ is the output vector. $\underline{\phi}(t)$ represents the modeling error between (1) and the SMM (3), which is mainly introduced by filter truncating. It will, obviously, approach to zero when the conditions in **Conclusion 2** are satisfied.

4 ADAPTIVE BLIND SIGNAL SEPARATION ALGORITHM

4.1 Blind signal separation using SMM

By defining $\underline{y}(t) \triangleq \mathbf{D}^{-1} * \underline{x}(t)$, we can get from SMM

$$\underline{y}(t) = \mathbf{H} * \underline{s}(t) + \mathbf{D}^{-1} * \underline{\phi}(t). \quad (4)$$

If the modeling error $\underline{\phi}(t)$ is much smaller than $\underline{x}(t)$, which is actually true if the conditions in **Conclusion 2** are satisfied and the length of Δh_{ij} 's is long enough, the second term on the right side of equation (4) will be approximately zero. As a consequence, the elements in the vector $\underline{y}(t)$ are mutually independent due to the diagonal matrix $\mathbf{H}$. Thus the objective of signal separation has been achieved.

Now we can see that the problem has changed to a blind separation of delayed and convolved sources. Other solutions for this problem can be found in recent years. [8] and [9] studied similar problems based on information maximization which implicitly uses HOS and increase the complexity. Above that these solutions did not consider the mixing model in a simple way and thus more filters had to be adjusted. In [10], in order to describe the difference between the paths from a source to all microphones only by time-delays, authors used a compact (1cm distance) microphone array. Unfortunately, such a array is not easy to be obtained for those

microphones having usual physical dimensions. Above that in a strongly reverberant environment another BSS algorithm will still be needed.

4.2 Frequency domain transformation

Since microphone signals are convolutive mixtures of original speech signals, a usual idea is to transform the mixed signals to frequency domain and then perform separation algorithms for each frequency bin as an instantaneous mixture case. In this paper we realize the separation algorithm by the same idea.

The discrete Fourier transform (DFT) allows us to express circular convolutions as products, while in (3) we assumed linear convolutions. However, in practice it is reasonable to express room impulse responses as FIR filters, so linear convolutions in (3) can be approximated by circular convolution if $P \ll N$, where P denotes the maximal length of filters in $\mathbf{H}$ and $\mathbf{D}$, and N denotes the number of points in the DFT. Also linear time-shifting in $\mathbf{D}$ can be approximated by circular time-shifting if $\tau_{max} \ll N$. Therefore, SMM may be rewritten approximately as

$$\underline{X}(\omega, t) = \mathcal{D}(\omega) \cdot \mathcal{H}(\omega) \cdot \underline{S}(\omega, t) + \underline{\Phi}(\omega, t), \quad (5)$$

where $\underline{X}(\omega, t)$ represents the DFT of the frame of size N starting at t , $[\underline{x}(t) \cdots \underline{x}(t + N - 1)]$, and is given by

$$\underline{X}(\omega, t) = \sum_{\kappa=0}^{N-1} e^{-j\omega\kappa} \underline{x}(t + \kappa), \quad \omega = 0, \frac{1}{N}2\pi, \dots, \frac{N-1}{N}2\pi.$$

$\underline{S}(\omega, t)$ and $\underline{\Phi}(\omega, t)$ are similar expressions as above. $\mathcal{H}(\omega)$ and $\mathcal{D}(\omega)$ denote the Fourier transform of the filter matrices $\mathbf{H}$ and $\mathbf{D}$, and $\mathcal{D}(\omega)$ can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{D}(\omega) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \cdots & \Delta H_{1n}(\omega)e^{-j\omega\tau_{1n}} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \Delta H_{n1}(\omega)e^{-j\omega\tau_{n1}} & \cdots & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

Define $\tilde{\underline{S}}(\omega, t) = \mathcal{H}(\omega) \cdot \underline{S}(\omega, t)$, then we have

$$\underline{X}(\omega, t) = \mathcal{D}(\omega) \cdot \tilde{\underline{S}}(\omega, t) + \underline{\Phi}(\omega, t). \quad (7)$$

4.3 Estimation algorithm for $\mathcal{D}(\omega)$

First we construct an output signal vector $\underline{Y}(\omega, t)$ using microphone signals $\underline{X}(\omega, t)$ and $\hat{\mathcal{D}}(\omega)$ which is the estimation of $\mathcal{D}(\omega)$ as follows:

$$\underline{Y}(\omega, t) = \hat{\mathcal{D}}^{-1}(\omega) \cdot \underline{X}(\omega, t), \quad (8)$$

and then introduce a cost function as follows

$$\begin{aligned} J(\hat{\mathcal{D}}(\omega)) &= \sum_{\omega} \sum_{i \neq j} |(\langle \underline{Y}(\omega, t) \underline{Y}^H(\omega, t) \rangle)_{ij}|^2, \\ &= \sum_{\omega} \sum_{i \neq j} |(\hat{\mathcal{D}}^{-1}(\omega) R_x(\omega) (\hat{\mathcal{D}}^{-1}(\omega))^H)_{ij}|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the expectation and $(\cdot)_{ij}$ denotes the i - j -element of a matrix. $R_x(\omega) = \langle \underline{X}(\omega, t) \underline{X}^H(\omega, t) \rangle$ represents the power matrix of $\underline{X}$ in each frequency bin.

The sum of crosscorrelations of elements in $\underline{Y}$ over all frequency bins is denoted by J . We will obtain $\widehat{\mathcal{D}}(\omega)$ by minimizing the cost function $J(\widehat{\mathcal{D}})$. When $\underline{\Phi}(\omega, t)$, under certain conditions shown in **Conclusion 2**, is very small comparative to $\underline{X}(\omega, t)$, $\widehat{\mathcal{D}}(\omega)$ will be the estimation of $\mathcal{D}(\omega)$.

4.3.1 A combined estimate algorithm

As seen in its definition, $J(\widehat{\mathcal{D}})$ is a very periodic function with respect to time delays τ_{ij} 's. Therefore, it is inevitable to be trapped in local optimum when minimizing J using usual gradient-based algorithms. To avoid this, a combined algorithm was proposed in [11]. Here we apply that algorithm and only show its skeleton in the following without details.

(i) Generate an initial set whose elements are all delay combinations like $\{\tau_{ij}\}$ randomly chosen from a uniform distribution $[-\tau_{max}, \tau_{max}]$. Each combination $\{\tau_{ij}\}$ corresponds to a candidate estimate of $\mathcal{D}$.

(ii) For each $\{\tau_{ij}\}$, calculate the minimum of $J(\widehat{\mathcal{D}})$ by the gradient descent algorithm, where the following gradients are used,

$$\frac{\partial J}{\partial \Delta H_{ij}(\omega)} = \left(\frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathcal{D}_{ij}(\omega)} \right)^* e^{j\omega\tau_{ij}}, \quad i \neq j, \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathcal{D}_{ij}(\omega)} &= \sum_{p \neq q} [(-\mathcal{D}^{-1}(\omega) E_{ij} R_D(\omega))_{qp} (R_D(\omega))_{pq} \\ &\quad + (R_D^*(\omega))_{pq} (-\mathcal{D}^{-1}(\omega) E_{ij} R_D(\omega))_{pq}], \\ &\quad p, q = 1, \dots, n, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$R_D(\omega) = \mathcal{D}^{-1}(\omega) R_x(\omega) [\mathcal{D}^{-1}(\omega)]^H, \quad (12)$$

where E_{ij} denotes a matrix whose ij -th element is one and others are zero, from which $\{\Delta H_{ij}(\omega)\}(\omega = 0, \frac{1}{N}2\pi, \dots, \frac{N-1}{N}2\pi)$ can be obtained iteratively.

(iii) Apply a genetic algorithm to generate a new set of $\{\tau_{ij}\}$'s according to the minimal values of $J(\widehat{\mathcal{D}})$ in (ii) and some genetic rules described in [11].

(iv) Repeat the above steps except (i) iteratively if the given searching times has not run out. Otherwise take the $\{\tau_{ij}\}$ and $\{\Delta H_{ij}(\omega)\}(\omega = 0, \frac{1}{N}2\pi, \dots, \frac{N-1}{N}2\pi)$ corresponding to the minimal $J(\widehat{\mathcal{D}})$ as the estimation of $\mathcal{D}(\omega)$.

We call the above steps a combined gradient-based genetic algorithm. The advantage of this algorithm is that it can avoid the local optimum as much as possible. However, the computation load is increased due to a number of searching loops. To make its implementation possible in real time, we will modify the algorithm here by removing the searching process.

4.3.2 Reduction of the computational complexity

In our SMM, the filters D_{ij} 's in the matrix $\mathbf{D}$ may be rewritten as

$$D_{ij} = \Delta h_{ij} * \delta(\tau_{ij}) = \Delta h'_{ij}. \quad (13)$$

where a filter $\Delta h'_{ij}$ replaces the original delay-filter combination. Therefore, the searching loops for τ_{ij} 's can be

omitted due to the absence of explicit time-delays. The arising problem is that the filter $\Delta h'_{ij}$ might be non-causal, e.g., in the case of $\tau_{ij} \in [-\tau_{max}, 0)$. As a solution, we can simply insert a certain number of delays τ' after each microphone signal $x_i(t)$. The matrix $\mathbf{D}$ is now changed to

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{pmatrix} \delta(\tau') & \dots & \Delta \tilde{h}_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \Delta \tilde{h}_{n1} & \dots & \delta(\tau') \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{D}(\omega) = \begin{pmatrix} e^{-j\omega\tau'} & \dots & \Delta \tilde{H}_{1n}(\omega) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \Delta \tilde{H}_{n1}(\omega) & \dots & e^{-j\omega\tau'} \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

where $\tau' \geq \tau_{max}$ (τ_{max} is determined by the maximal distance between microphones) and $\Delta \tilde{h}_{ij} = \delta(\tau') * \Delta h'_{ij}$ is a causal filter whose length is $\tilde{P} \ll N$. $\mathcal{D}(\omega)$ is the Fourier transform of $\mathbf{D}$. Then the estimation of $\mathcal{D}(\omega)$ may be realized by a usual gradient descent algorithm using gradients

$$\frac{\partial J}{\partial \Delta \tilde{H}_{ij}(\omega)} = \left(\frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathcal{D}_{ij}(\omega)} \right)^*, \quad i \neq j. \quad (15)$$

$\frac{\partial J}{\partial \mathcal{D}_{ij}(\omega)}$ has the same form as (11) where $\mathcal{D}(\omega)$ is shown in (14). The computation load is considerably reduced.

4.3.3 Convolution constraints

The frequency domain filters will no longer correspond to time domain filters of length $\tilde{P}$ if the above gradients are used. The gradients have to be constrained to the subspace where using them we can get solutions as $\Delta \tilde{h}_{ij}(t) = 0(t > \tilde{P})$. This is also important for equation (5) to have a good approximation.

Here we use the following simple method which have appeared in previous literature (e.g., [6]),

$$\frac{\partial J}{\partial \Delta \tilde{H}_{ij}(\omega)} := \mathcal{F} \mathbf{Z} \mathcal{F}^{-1} \frac{\partial J}{\partial \Delta \tilde{H}_{ij}(\omega)}, \quad (16)$$

where $\frac{\partial J}{\partial \Delta \tilde{H}_{ij}(\omega)} = [\frac{\partial J}{\partial \Delta \tilde{H}_{ij}(0)}, \dots, \frac{\partial J}{\partial \Delta \tilde{H}_{ij}(\frac{N-1}{N}2\pi)}]^T$, $\mathcal{F}$ is a Fourier matrix with $(\mathcal{F})_{kl} = e^{-j2\pi(k-1)(l-1)/N}$ ($k, l = 1, \dots, N$) and $\mathbf{Z}$ is diagonal with $Z_{ii} = 1$ for $i \leq \tilde{P}$ and $Z_{ii} = 0$ for $i > \tilde{P}$. The constraints also have the effect of restricting the solutions to be smooth in the frequency domain because of the fact that not all permutations over frequencies will lead to FIR filters which satisfy the constraints. Some details of this issue can be found in [6].

4.4 Power matrix update

The initial power matrix $R_x(\omega)$ may be approximately calculated by

$$R_x(\omega) \approx \frac{1}{2T} \sum_{l=0}^{2T-1} \underline{X}(\omega, l) \underline{X}^H(\omega, l) \quad (17)$$

because of the temporary stationarity of human voices within a quite short time (about a few 10msecs). On the other hand, we have to update the power matrix $R_x(\omega)$ during signal separation due to its non-stationarity. The updating can be realized as the following:

$$R_x(\omega) := \alpha R_x(\omega) + (1 - \alpha) \underline{X}(\omega, t) \underline{X}^H(\omega, t), \quad (18)$$

where α is forgetting factor and usually is chosen near 1, e.g., $\alpha = 0.99$ which is optimal for nearly stationary signals.

4.5 Acquisition of unmixed signals

Having got the estimated value $\widehat{\mathcal{D}}(\omega)$, equation (8) may be used to perform filtering efficiently in frequency domain. Then applying the overlap-save method the separated output $\underline{y}(t)$ may be obtained.

Note that when being implemented in real time, the estimation of $\mathcal{D}(\omega)$ and the updating of $R_x(\omega)$ may be combined to reduce the computational complexity.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Experiments are done with speech signals recorded in a real acoustic environment. The dimensions of the room used for recording are $5.2 \times 3.8 \times 3.4\text{m}$ (l**x**b**x**h). Two male speakers simultaneously read 4 sentences aloud. The distance between them is 80cm. The mixed signals are recorded by two microphones spaced 58cm apart. Both the speakers are about 1.2m away from their microphones. The recordings are of 16 bit precision, sampled at 16 kHz and a duration of 10 seconds. The DFT used in the experiment is of length 512. The forgetting factor in cross power estimation is fixed to be $\alpha = 0.98$.

For the difference filter Δh_{ij} , experiments have been done with different lengths (from 32 to 128). We can hear from all the results that crosstalk has been considerably reduced so as not to be disturbing when listening to either of the separated signals. Increasing the length of Δh_{ij} gives slightly different separated outputs in this case. The results of only using the filter of length 32 are shown below (first 5 seconds).

Figure 1: The left are microphone signals (top x_1 and bottom x_2) and the right are separated signals (top y_1 and bottom y_2).

6 CONCLUSIONS

A new blind separation algorithm is presented which is based on a simplified mixing model and only use second order statistics. Experiment results show that the algorithm is effective when applied to real world audio separation in a usual reverberant environment. Its main

advantage over other BSS algorithms is the significant reduction of parameters to be estimated, which makes it less time and power consuming and more easily implemented in real time.

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